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Understanding Wildfires in Norway: Key Hazards and Vegetation Fires Damaging Buildings 2016–2023

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ABSTRACT

Wildland–urban interface (WUI) fires are an increasing global challenge, and local knowledge is essential for efficient mitigation. In Norway, as for the rest of Northern Europe, wildfires are expected to increase in frequency and severity, which will also increase WUI vulnerabilities. This study analyzes all registered vegetation fires damaging buildings in Norway from January 2016 to April 2023 (74 fires damaging 102 structures), with a case-by-case review of 18 fires impacting two or more structures. We have identified that spring season fires and direct flame contact are the primary contributors to vegetation fires that damage buildings in Norway. We also provide insights from three wildfire exercises with prescribed burns and a post-fire evaluation, providing fire dynamics data on fires in low vegetation while identifying a need to focus on hazards related to juniper vegetation and unmanaged cultural landscapes. This new knowledge is vital for developing effective and targeted prevention measures for Norwegian communities in WUI areas.

1 | Introduction

Climate change, along with shifts in land use and rising populations, is increasing the frequency and intensity of wildfires and wildland–urban interface (WUI) fires, and expanding the regions they affect. As urban areas encroach on wildlands, WUI areas become more vulnerable, posing significant challenges to coexistence and safety. In Norway, although wildfires have been less frequent than in southern Europe, they are expected to increase in both frequency and severity due to climate change and population growth, mirroring global trends [1–6].

The winter wildfires of 2014 [7] and the wildfire season of 2018 [8, 9] in Norway and Scandinavia highlight the urgent need for effective prevention and preparedness measures to mitigate future wildfire losses. As an example, high winds and drought facilitated the spread of the 2014 Flatanger winter coastal

wildfire, which resulted in the loss of 63 buildings, marking it as the largest WUI fire in Norway to date [7]. This and similar fires have demonstrated several key challenges specific to Norway's WUI areas, such as building traditions relying on wooden construction materials, the dispersed rural settlements and vacation homes in intermixed WUI areas, and the extensive infrastructure that includes telecommunications and power supply, stretching ~1800 km from north to south and along a coastline of about 100 000 km. Therefore, there is a pressing need for more knowledge and innovative strategies to manage and adapt to the increasing threat and the devastating consequences of WUI fires in Norway.

Mitigating the social and economic impacts of wildfires requires a comprehensive approach, involving the characterization and reduction of hazards, the reduction of vulnerabilities, and effective response and recovery strategies [10]. Efficient mitigation

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efforts in the WUI require local knowledge of relevant and targeted measures.

The *characterization of wildfire hazards* in a location involves analyzing the available fuel types and their burning behavior. Wildfire hazard maps show the hazard level, and obtaining reliable, high-quality maps requires sufficient quantity and quality data, including data on the thermal intensity (flame length, temperatures) and propagation speed of wildfires in the area [10]. In terms of volume, the most prominent tree species in Norway are Norwegian spruce (*Picea abies*), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), and birch (*Betula pubescens* most common, but *Betula pendula* and *Betula nana* are also found in Norwegian nature) [11, 12]. On the coastline, there are heathlands dominated by heather (*Calluna vulgaris*) and other low-growing shrubs, sedges, herbs, and grasses [13]. While the literature provides some insight into wildfires involving these species, knowledge gaps remain in documenting the relevance to Norwegian forests and coastal landscapes, particularly in identifying key natural hazards and documenting the fire dynamics.

To *reduce vulnerabilities* in structures and buildings in the WUI area, it is essential to understand the common fire spread mechanisms in the given region (*characterize the hazard*). For example, the mitigating measures differ for fires spreading with flying embers versus direct flame contact. Across the globe, several recommendations and guidelines have been developed to support local communities and policymakers to reduce the damage caused by WUI fires. Examples include “FireWise” from the United States by the NFPA [14], “FireSmart” from Canada by the Canadian Interagency Forest Fire Centre [15], and “National Guide for Wildland Urban interface fires” from Canada by the National Research Council of Canada [16]. For many of these locations flying embers are the most frequent fire spread mechanism [17, 18]. However, a recent study in Sweden [19] documented that direct flame contact was the main driver behind the destruction of 187 buildings during the 2018 wildfire season, indicating that Scandinavian vegetation fires require different mitigation approaches to reduce vulnerabilities in WUI areas.

In this study, we analyzed statistics from all registered fires in Norway where a vegetation fire spread to buildings in the period January 2016 to April 2023. A case-by-case review is conducted on nearly all such fires that affected two or more structures during this period. The data is compared with the findings from three wildfire exercises involving prescribed burns in boreal and coastal landscapes, as well as one post-fire evaluation of a coastal wildfire. We present our findings with the aim to support knowledge-based, targeted, and relevant mitigation measures to *reduce vulnerabilities* in Norwegian WUI communities.

2 | Case Study: Statistics and Data on Vegetation Fires Damaging Buildings in Norway

This section presents data from all registered vegetation fires that have spread to one or more buildings in Norway between January 2016 and April 2023, along with a case-by-case review

of selected fires, with the aim of understanding when and how structures were ignited in WUI areas across the country.

Statistics on past vegetation fires affecting buildings were collected from the national Norwegian fire statistics database called BRIS [20]. Fires included in the data set are any fire that started in nature and affected buildings, given by the pre-determined registration options in the database of a fire in nature (Norwegian: “Brann i gress-eller innmark/Brann i skog-eller utmark”), *combined with* a registration that this fire has spread to a dwelling, industry building, garage, or other building (Norwegian: “Spredning til bolig/næringsbygg/garasje/andre bygg”). The publicly available dataset includes information on the date, type of wildfire, the municipality where the fire occurred, and the fire service responsible for responding. The cause of the vegetation fire is not included.

In addition to the data from BRIS [20], data on the type and number of buildings that each of these fires had spread to was provided upon request by the owner of the database, the Norwegian Directorate of Civil Protection (DSB). The exact locations of the fires are not specified, and the locations presented in this study are the locations of the relevant fire service or the municipality's city center.

A total of 74 vegetation fires affecting buildings were registered during the investigated period, averaging ~10 fires per year over the course of 7 years. The total number of damaged buildings and structures in the data set is 102. An overview of the location and time of year for each fire is given in Figure 1 (left). In Figure 1 (top right) the fires are sorted per county, and in Figure 1 (bottom right) fires per 100000 inhabitants per county are presented, based on data from Statistics Norway's table “06913” for population and changes, per region, variable, and year (Befolkning og endringer, etter region, statistikkvariabel og år).

The results in Figure 1 (left) show that 76% of WUI fires occur during March ($n=12$), April ($n=29$), and May ($n=15$) (see Figure 1, left). This indicates that springtime is a high-hazard period for WUI fires in Norway. Several factors might contribute to this elevated hazard. First, spring is often characterized by dry conditions following the winter thaw. As snow melts and moisture levels in vegetation decrease, combustible materials like dry grass, leaves, and dead wood accumulate, creating fuel for potential fires. Warmer temperatures combined with low humidity and wind can dry out vegetation, increasing its flammability. Human activity also tends to rise in spring as milder weather encourages outdoor activities like hiking and camping, which can lead to accidental fires. Additionally, activities such as controlled burning, land clearing, and machinery use outdoors increase, adding to the fire hazard.

The data per county indicate that there is a positive correlation between the total number of fires and the population of each county (Figure 1, top right). The counties of Troms og Finnmark, Nordland, and Møre og Romsdal have the lowest population numbers and are also among the counties with a low number of WUI fires, while Viken County, which has the largest population of all the counties, recorded the highest number of WUI fires. This suggests that human activity is a key contributor to

FIGURE 1 | Overview of the 74 vegetation fires that damaged one or more buildings in Norway during 2016–2023 (here denoted as WUI fires). Left: Map showing the approximate fire locations, color-coded by month of the year. Top right: Number of WUI fires as a function of population (given in thousands) in all of Norway’s counties, with a linear trendline ($R^2=0.56$) indicating the correlation between the total number of fires and the population in the county. The two counties of Nordland and Troms og Finnmark have overlapping data positions. Bottom right: Number of registered WUI fires per 100000 inhabitants sorted by county, with the geographical region of the county given in parentheses, with the most WUI fires per inhabitant registered in the North, followed by Mid, East, West, and finally South Norway. The county structure of 11 counties in Norway per 1 January 2023 is used. Maps Data: Google, @2024 GeoBasis-DE/BKG (@2009), an online, interactive map is available here: <https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/edit?mid=1-mP3eTyHiHiD4vdFbZ-lcKizJQRoVQU&usp=sharing>.

fire ignition, as further highlighted in the case-by-case review. In contrast to this trend, Oslo County has only one reported WUI fire ($n = 1$), despite its high population. The county of Rogaland was the only county with no reported fires, but it is included in the data set to show the full list of Norway’s 11 counties per 2023. When removing Rogaland from the data set, the correlation is stronger, with $R^2 = 0.62$ versus 0.56. This indicates that the type of settlement (urban versus rural) may influence the number of WUI fires, and Figure 1 (bottom right) indicates that counties with significant rural populations, such as Viken, Innlandet, Nordland, and Troms og Finnmark, experience a higher number of WUI fires per inhabitant compared with counties with larger urban areas and fewer wildland spaces, like Oslo.

To study this in detail, the data is presented at a municipal level in Figure 2. The data was obtained by using the following tables from Statistics Norway, “06265” for the number of buildings in the municipalities (Boliger, etter region, statistikkvariabel, år og byggingstype), “11342” for area and population by municipality (Areal og befolkning, etter region, statistikkvariabel og år), and “05212” for the amount of people in sparsely populated areas (Folkemengde, etter kjønn og tettbygd/spredtbygd strøk 1990–2024). Statistics Norway defines a sparsely populated area as a cluster of buildings with less than 200 inhabitants, and the distance between the buildings normally exceeds 50m, and each municipality may thus be grouped as a rural, semi-rural, or urban settlement.

FIGURE 2 | Overview on a municipal level, over vegetation fires damaging buildings (WUI fires) per 10000 inhabitants as a function of buildings per km² in that municipality, with a power trend line added for all fires ($R^2=0.56$). Rural settlements are municipalities with >66% sparsely populated areas, semi-urban 33%–66%, and urban settlements <33%. Two special cases are not shown in the graph for clarity, but are included in the statistical analysis of the data set. These are municipalities with very high population numbers: Bærum with 0.184 fires per 10000 inhabitants and 288 buildings per km² and Oslo with 0.028 fires per 10000 inhabitants and 829 buildings per km².

FIGURE 3 | (a) Overview of the 19 vegetation fires that damaged two or more buildings in Norway during 2016–2023. The map shows the approximate fire locations, color coded by fire spread mode. The circles mark the (b) and (c) photos' fire locations. (b) The barn that burned down in the Lurøy fire of May 2018, and (c) the Sunndal fire of March 2016. Photos by Nordmøre and Romsdal Fire and Rescue Service, and Lurøy fire and rescue service, used with permission. Maps Data: Google, ©2024 GeoBasis-DE/BKG (©2009), an online, interactive map is available here: https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/edit?mid=1xCVLGXDtmZ_WgEpTxIWmPQiW9SiI3Rk&usp=sharing.

There is no statistically significant difference in the number of WUI fires per inhabitant between the three groups of rural, semi-rural, and urban settlements (Kruskal–Wallis test, significance level 0.05). However, there is a correlation between the number of WUI fires per inhabitant and the number of buildings per area (when applying a power trend line to the data, giving a reasonable fit, $R^2 = 0.56$). As the number of buildings per km^2 increases, WUI fires become less common. This can be attributed to the fact that when more buildings are constructed, the natural vegetation that typically fuels wildfires is often cleared or reduced. This creates buffer zones with less combustible material, making it more difficult for fires to spread. Another contributing factor can be the use of cabins and holiday homes during weekends and vacations, which is a strong tradition in Norway. In municipalities with many cabins, there can be many buildings per km^2 , but few registered residential inhabitants. The current data set does not account for the use of cabins and holiday homes, but this could be a contributing factor to the observed trends.

For vegetation fires affecting two or more structures (19 of the 74), details on each fire were collected by contacting each local fire service via email and telephone. Information was collected for 18 of 19 cases. The most common documented mechanism of fire spread was direct flame contact, which occurred in 8 of 18 documented cases. In 6 cases, the mechanism was unknown, 1 case was likely due to spotting (ignition by flying embers), and 3 reports were determined to be faulty (reporting wildfires with no damaged structures) (see Figure 3a).

For the 8 fires with direct flame contact, the observed spread mode is based on visual observations during the event. In one case, the fire service noted that the fire intensified when it spread uphill. For the one that was reported as spotting, the fire service stated that the spread mechanism was most likely due to spotting, as the fire was not in direct contact with the structure, yet “suddenly” the structure caught fire. Due to the relatively few number of such fires per year, the total number of vegetation fires affecting two or more structures is not large enough to allow for a statistical analysis of the data for the available 7-year period.

Table 1 presents each of the 19 fires in chronological order. Several fires were initiated by human activity, including three prescribed burns that got out of control, one incident of unsafe hot works using an angle grinder, one barbecue, and one case of suspected arson.

2.1 | Method Limitations

The statistical data set has several limitations. First, not all fires are registered in the national database for various reasons. Second, the data that is mandatory to enter is limited, and detailed, high-quality information on each fire is often unavailable, even upon direct request. Third, variations in reporting practices among fire services lead to inconsistencies, such as differing thresholds for registering a building as

TABLE 1 | Overview of 19 vegetation fires damaging buildings in Norway during 2016–2023, where two or more structures were damaged.

Location	Date	Cause of wildfire	Fire spread mode to structure	Comment
Sunnal	March 2016	Prescribed burn-out of control	Flame contact	Unpredictable winds and dry conditions. A building under construction with exposed plastic insulation caught fire. The fire partly damaged the building and spread to surrounding buildings (Figure 3c).
Kongsberg	February 2016	Sparks from an angle grinder	Unknown	Sparks ignited hay and burned three unidentified buildings. The fire burned a total of 35 ha.
Oslo	June 2016	Possibly arson	Unknown	The police have commented that there were some matches around the area where the fire started.
Aurskog-Hørland	June 2016	Unknown	Unknown	Very little information. No indication of the ignition method or how the fire started.
Øystre Sildre	May 2017	N/A	Faulty report	No buildings burned.
Åmli	April 2018	Unknown	Unknown	Very little information. No indication of the ignition method or how the fire started.
Lurøy	May 2018	Not specified	Spotting	A barn was “suddenly on fire.” The fire service hypothesized fire spread due to spotting. Another building was surrounded by fire but did not ignite (Figure 3b).
Bærum	June 2018	N/A	Faulty report	No buildings burned
Kongsberg	July 2018	Unknown	Unknown	This fire had already ignited a vacation residence when the fire service arrived. Very dry and hot Scandinavian summer causing a lot of fires with unknown ignition points. The fire burned a total of 4.2 ha.
Sarpsborg	July 2018	Bird flying into power line	Flame contact	A woodpecker flew into a power line and the sparks ignited a fire. The statistics state that 4 buildings burned but according to the fire service only one house was affected. The fire spread through flame contact to a veranda but was contained before it spread to the building.
Inderøy	April 2019	Prescribed burn-out of control	Flame contact	The fire started from a prescribed burn that got out of control. Two houses were affected. There was a lot of old, tall, dead grass around the buildings that facilitated the flame contact to the buildings. One house was saved by the presence of a low stone foundation that hindered flame contact.

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Location	Date	Cause of wildfire	Fire spread mode to structure	Comment
Åfjord	April 2019	Barbeque	Flame contact	A group of kids and one adult were on an excursion to barbeque on a disposable grill. A piece of the paper that was used to ignite the disposable grill was caught by the wind and landed in some dry grass which then spread rapidly due to the windy conditions. The fire spread to the building through flame contact.
Rælingen	April 2020	Unknown	Flame contact	Small fire with unknown origin. Not much info, but the fire service state that the fire most likely spread to the structure through flame contact.
Tjelsund	May 2020	—	—	No info provided.
Austevoll	March 2021	N/A	Faulty report	No buildings burned.
Tromsø	May 2021	Not specified	Flame contact	Fire spread to several garages and cars through flame contact. Fire spread rapidly up a slope toward the buildings. The fire cause was not specified.
Øygarden	June 2021	Unknown	Unknown	Fire services report states that two buildings were affected, but no details on fire ignition or spread.
Kongsvinger	April 2022	Unknown	Flame contact	Fire spread to an abandoned house through flame contact.
Balsfjord	June 2022	Prescribed burn out of control	Flame contact	The fire started from a prescribed burn that got out of control. Two houses were burned to the ground and two more were flame impinged. There was a lot of old, tall, dead grass around the buildings that facilitated the flame contact to the buildings.

Note: The location is the municipality of the fire.

affected, which range from light charring to severe charring or complete burn-down. These variations are evident in cases where free-text information is provided and from direct communication with selected fire services. Fourth, there were not many severe wildfires during the investigated time period; most were small intentional burns getting out of control, limiting the data set.

As mentioned, the population data is based on registered residential addresses and does not take into account the use of holiday homes or cabins.

The qualitative data collected in this study was not derived from systematic interviews with transcripts but rather gathered from various smaller inputs and sources provided to the authors over the course of the study.

3 | Field Studies-Results From Prescribed Burns and A Post-Fire Evaluation

To better understand wildfire hazards in WUI areas, prescribed burns offer controlled environments where fire behavior—including fire spread rates and temperature measurements—can be systematically observed. While not fully representative of free-burning wildfires, prescribed burns may feature free-burning sections, allowing researchers to study fire spread under realistic conditions while adhering to safety protocols. The resulting data, both empirical and quantitative, give valuable insights into fire dynamics, helping us understand the specific wildfire hazards in Norway.

Prescribed burns also offer another important aspect to safeguard WUI areas in Norway—firefighter training and exchange of best

FIGURE 4 | The prescribed burn exercise at Kvam: (a) The map overview of the test field, instrumentation and important locations. Note that only fields A and B had burns giving temperature data recordings. (b) The instrumentation poles placed on Zone A. (c) Ignition from the 2nd ignition point, (d) Burnt vegetation on Zone A.

practices. As shown in the historic data above, wildfires in WUI areas can be unintentionally sparked by human activity. Several stakeholders in this study emphasized that even prescribed burns—planned and executed by professionals—can lead to unintentional fire spread. This highlights the critical importance of understanding and implementing safe practices for prescribed burns, so that training of firefighter personnel and reduction of natural fuel loads may be maintained, while simultaneously minimizing the chance of accidental ignition in vulnerable areas.

In this study, prescribed burns are used to document fire behavior and to identify best practices for safely conducting these controlled fires. A post-fire evaluation is also included to gain insight into learning points from a real wildfire to address Norwegian WUI vulnerabilities.

3.1 | Field Exercise With Prescribed Burn, Kvam

In May 2023, a wildfire exercise was performed in Tørvikbygd, Kvam municipality in Vestland county (Figure 4a). The region is inland, but by the Hardanger fjord. The exercise area was a 130 m by 430 m hill, and the vegetation was mainly bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus*), bog bilberry (*Vaccinium uliginosum*), grasses, mosses, Scots pines, and juniper bushes (*Juniperus communis*). The exercise included 13 fire services and other wildfire management stakeholders. Fires were ignited using drip torches, with some areas burning naturally and others influenced by proximity to ignition points.

The area of the field exercise in Kvam, May 2023, is outlined in Figure 2a. In total, 20 instrumentation poles (Figure 4b), each containing two TCs (1.5 mm type K, positioned at 0 and 75 cm above the ground) and one plate TC (positioned at 75 cm above the ground), seven cameras (GoPro) and one weather station (Kestrel 550FWL) were placed to measure the temperature, heat flux, flame spread rate (based on video recordings), residency time (based on temp > 25°C), and wind speed and direction. Two types of plate TCs were used for heat flux documentation, a fast-response type with 0.4 mm Inconel steel, 1 mm type K TC, backed with 5 cm refractory insulation, and a standardized type [21] with 0.7 mm Inconel steel, 1 mm type K TC, backed with 1 cm ceramic insulation.

The poles were placed in a linear formation across four zones, A, B, C, and D, with a 5 m distance between each pole. Free-burn fires were recorded in both zones A and B, where terrain slopes were manually recorded to be 8.1° at the steepest part of zone A and 6.8° at the steepest part of zone B. The vegetation was documented by visual observations and photos of the macroscopic-level landscape. For fuel characterization, vegetation samples representative of the surroundings were collected and placed in airtight bags. The fuel load per area was documented for one 0.25 m × 0.25 m sample without a humus layer per field, separating living and dead material, drying, and weighing. Smaller samples of individual species were collected, and the fuel moisture content (FMC) was documented by drying the sample at 105°C and weighing every 24 h until stable weight (< 0.1 g change), calculated as $FMC = (\text{fresh mass of sample} - \text{dry mass of sample}) / \text{dry mass of sample}$. Visual observations

were also made from a distance of the fires in areas that were not monitored by instruments or recorded on video. The fire service's actions during the exercise were observed, and any lessons learned were discussed with the fire services and other stakeholders.

The wind speed during the exercise was between 0.5 and 3.5 m/s, the main wind directions were south-east and south-west, and the air temperature was 9°C–12°C.

The exercise began with a firefighter igniting the fire in front of Zone A using a drip torch, following the path shown in Figure 4a. Additionally, the fire service established three other ignition points to study flame spread across different types of vegetation and terrain. The second ignition point had live, tall pine trees on a moderately uphill slope (Figure 4c), while the third and fourth ignition points were on steep uphill slopes, with the third having previously cut and piled vegetation, and the fourth having sparse vegetation. Two helicopters and more than 60 firefighters joined the exercise to practice the wildfire response methods and tools. Weather data showed wind speed (avg. ~2.25 m/s, range 0.5–4.0 m/s) and direction (W) during the exercise.

The gravimetric water content in the ground during the exercise was about 400%, making ignition difficult. After the successful ignition at Zone A, the fire spread to Zone B. Flame residence times in naturally spreading fires ranged from 2.30 to 3.77 min, with maximum temperatures at 0 cm above the ground reaching 511°C in Zone A, where the flame front spread rate was estimated at 0.39 m/min. Heat flux measured 75 cm above the ground in Zone A was a maximum of 1.3 kW/m² measured by the standard plate TCs (no natural burn recording near the fast-response plate TC). In Zone B, flame residence times ranged from 2.30 to 3.37 min, with maximum temperatures at 0 cm above the ground between 51°C and 381°C. Near the fourth instrumentation pole at Zone B, the flame front spread rate was measured at 0.22 m/min. Heat flux measured 75 cm above the ground in Zone B was a maximum of 2.1 kW/m² measured by the standard plate TC, and a maximum of 12.5 kW/m² measured by the fast-response plate TC. The FMC of the vegetation ranged from 26%–38% in the dead grass and up to 380% in other vegetation, leading to slow fire spread. Forested areas accumulated significantly more dead material compared with open areas, with dry weight ranging from 111 to 1568 g/m². This higher dead fuel load in forested areas may have contributed to increased fire potential. The results align with visual observations, with generally slow fire spreads due to high moisture. Small areas with persistent smoldering and glowing fires were also observed the next day, some quite active with an occasional transition to flaming. After the exercise, hot spot monitoring of the site was performed to prevent potential escalation.

3.2 | Field Exercise With Prescribed Burn, Drangedal

An emergency preparedness exercise including prescribed burns and firefighting drills was hosted in May 2024 in Drangedal municipality, in the county of Vestfold og Telemark. The host of the exercise was a local fire service, in collaboration with the national civil protection authorities and the civil defense. The area of the exercise was a cordoned-off shooting range in an open marsh with surrounding forest, where prescribed burns were done both on

the dry open marsh and in a cut forest area. Observations were made of free burns within selected areas, with boundaries limited by dry and wet fire breaks, made manually by the fire service and by helicopters. Visual observations and cameras were used for the documentation of flame front spread rate, flame length, and residence time. The vegetation was documented as for Kvam (see above). Wind speed, wind direction, and air temperature were documented using a weather station (Kestrel 550FWL).

The wind speed during the exercise was 0.5–4 m/s, with shifting wind direction and air temperature of 13°C–15°C.

The cut forested area (sector 1) was populated by dead grass (FMC 11%–20%), small Scots pines (FMC of the shoots were 111%), Juniper (FMC 109%), and heather (FMC 67%–68%) (Figure 5b,e). During the free burn, the dead grass had a spread rate of 1.3 m/min and flame lengths up to 0.3 m (max. 1 m in certain areas). Junipers produced large flames, with heights ranging from 0.5 to 3 m and reaching a maximum of 6 m in isolated instances. When the junipers were ignited by the lower vegetation, the fire spread quickly vertically, and one side of the bush could burn and become completely charred while the other side remained intact. Heather, with a moderate moisture content, burned with flame lengths of 1.0–1.5 m, and the fire spread more slowly than the grass fire but showed a long residence time of about 80 s in some areas. During the exercise, after 1 min of burning, the fire spread from a juniper to the lower branches of a Spruce tree (7 m tall), which started to burn intensely. It took only 30 s from the first ignition of the lowest branches of the spruce to become fully engulfed with a maximal flame length of 15 m, and another 30 s until burn-out (Figure 5b). The juniper in this case acted as a ladder for the fire to climb to the lower branches of the Spruce.

As shown in Figure 5a,c,d the dry open marsh (sector 2) was populated mainly by dead grass (FMC 14%–25%), moss (FMC 725%), and bog bilberry (*Vaccinium uliginosum*, FMC 130%–145%—reflecting its growth pattern—rooted in the moist moss layer but exposed to air, allowing for faster drying). Here, the dead grass showed a spread rate of 0.6–1.2 m/min with flame lengths of 0.1–0.3 m (up to 0.4 m in windy conditions). Bog bilberry with higher FMC had a slower spread rate of 0.5 m/min, but flame lengths reached up to 0.5 m (1 m in windy conditions). In contrast, the moss did not burn significantly, reflecting its high moisture content. Post-flaming smoldering fires were observed in both locations.

These data (Table 2) underline the critical role vegetation type and moisture content play in influencing fire behavior, highlighting the importance of moisture sampling in fire spread prediction. It also provides important information to understand vegetation's role in fire dynamics and provides insights for future prescribed burn strategies.

During the exercise, it was noted that a significant amount of fire smoke was generated, especially during low-intensity flaming and smoldering periods, underlining the need to use respiratory protective equipment and other personal protective equipment during such exercises to limit exposure to toxic and carcinogenic smoke.

Another general learning point that stakeholders in the exercise emphasized was the key role of helicopters and drones

FIGURE 5 | The prescribed burn exercise in Drangedal, May 2024. Sector 1 was a cut forested area (b, e) and sector 2 was a dry open marsh (a, c, d).

TABLE 2 | Overview of vegetation types, their measured fuel moisture contents (FMC) and observed flame front spread rates, flame lengths, and residence times. Not all information was collected for all vegetation types.

Vegetation type (sector number)	Flame front spread rate (m/min)	Flame length avg (m)	Flame length max (m)	Residence time (s)	FMC (wt%)
Dead grass (S2)	0.6–1.2	0.1–0.3	0.4	4–12	14–25
Bog bilberry, <i>Vaccinium uliginosum</i> (S2)	0.5	0.4–0.5	1.0	4–12	130–145
Moss (S2)	Minimal burn	Minimal burn	—	—	725
Dead grass (S1)	1.3	0.3	1.0	—	11–20
Juniper, <i>Juniperus communis</i> (S1)	— ^a	0.5–3.0	0.6	—	111
Heather, <i>Calluna vulgaris</i> (S1)	— ^b	1.0–1.5	1.5	80	67–68

^aThe juniper plants were ignited by the surrounding lower vegetation and not by each other.

^bThe fire spread in the heather could not be observed accurately due to the smoke, but it had similar spread rates as for the dead grass.

during both wildfire exercises and real wildfire events. Helicopters were utilized to make wet fire breaks and thus enable rapid changes in the response if needed. In addition, drones were used to support situational awareness for the team leaders.

3.3 | Field Exercises With Prescribed Burn, Haugalandet

In the southwestern coastal landscapes of Haugalandet, there is an active volunteer community that performs prescribed burns to maintain the cultural heritage landscapes and for fuel management. Through a field visit with visual

observations and analysis of photo series from the prescribed burns (Figure 6), we have identified some key lessons for understanding the hazards along the coast. For prescribed springtime burns of heather and grass fires, as long as the wind conditions are calm and moisture in the ground is high, the observed flame intensities are low and only able to burn the surface of the biomass, that is, the top layer of light, dead grass (Figure 6a,b,e). For prescribed burns with more intense wind conditions, faster fire spread rates and more intense fires are observed. An example is shown in Figure 6d, where the relative humidity was 39%, air temperature 9°C, and wind speed 5–8 m/s, giving a relatively fast fire spread rate of ~6 m/min through moss and juniper vegetation, with flame lengths estimated to be 0.3–1.0 m, estimated from a photo series.

FIGURE 6 | Prescribed burns in the coastal landscapes of Haugalandet, South-Western Norway. Prescribed burn outside Haugesund, February 2023 (a, b) showing low-intensity burns, except for overgrown junipers (c) burning intensely. In Karmøy, April 2022, 39% humidity and 5–8 m/s winds gave a relatively fast fire spread rate of ~6 m/min (d). Controlled burn in Sveio, Spring 2023 (e). Photos by RISE Fire Research/TREEADS, Annelaug Fludal, and Åshild Irene Lie, used with permission.

The local fire services and volunteer communities emphasize the drastic changes in recent decades in the landscapes along the coastline. Changes in farming practices, fewer sheep and goats to graze the natural vegetation, and fewer prescribed burns result in an overgrown coastline with an abundance of natural fuels and less experience within the community on how to conduct safe prescribed burns. When performing prescribed burns, they have identified overgrown junipers (Figure 6c) that grow taller than 1 m as a particular cause for concern. Juniper can require longer heat exposure to ignite compared with, for example, grass, but with thin and oily needles, they burn intensely once ignited. The invasive Sitka spruce is also identified as a hazardous species that the locals work to remove.

3.4 | Post-Wildfire Inspection in Roan

A wildfire occurred in Roan municipality in Trøndelag county in November 2022 [22] (Figure 7a,b). This was an unusual winter wildfire event in coastal Norway. The fire spread rapidly due to dry vegetation and heavy winds, threatening homes and power lines. During the response, the local emergency services were supported by the civil defense, the Red Cross, and the military. A wildfire helicopter and personnel for decision support from the national civil protection authorities were utilized, as well as a drone for situational awareness and hot spot detection. The response successfully prevented escalation, and the fire did not spread to any structures.

A post-fire site visit was made 2 days after the flame-out (Figure 7c,e). The area has typical Norwegian coastal landscapes

with hills, bilberry, heather (*Calluna vulgaris*), grass, moss, small pine and birch trees, and juniper vegetation. In addition, there are planted spruce forested areas. Visual inspections of the fire site revealed mostly superficial burns, with charring depths of 0.005–0.01 m, and deeper burns of up to 0.1 m in sheltered areas. The variations in local vegetation combined with a hilly terrain contributed to observed variations in burn intensities. Residual smoldering was observed in the field 2 days after flame-out, emphasizing the need for post-fire monitoring of hot spots (Figure 7d).

Learning points on the fire response were collected through discussion with the three incident chiefs at the local fire service and by review of their incident evaluation report (not public, available upon request). Some key challenges during the response were the long travel distances for key personnel, coordination, and communication. Being a rural area with a part-time fire service, the local fire service emphasized the importance of training and coordinated efforts, as well as collaborations, for example, with the use of advanced equipment such as drones for hot spot monitoring and decision support.

3.5 | Method Limitations

The field exercises were organized by local fire services, and in some instances, time constraints or miscommunication affected the data collection at certain sites. The data presented in this study is only based on the free-burn of natural vegetation. Any data points suspected to be impacted by gasoline from drip

FIGURE 7 | The Roan wildfire (b) in November 2022 threatened homes and power lines (c). Superficial burns, with local deeper burns, were observed at a post-fire inspection (a, e), and an active smoldering hot spot generated glowing, flying embers.

torches have been excluded, and fire dynamics have only been recorded when helicopters have not altered the wind conditions.

4 | Discussion and Conclusions

4.1 | Characterizing Wildfire Hazards Based on Historical Data

There are about 10 registered vegetation fires spreading to buildings in Norway per year during the study period, with a total of 74 fires damaging 102 structures, with a subset involving two or more structures of 19 fires. This indicates that WUI fires are not very frequent in Norway. As mentioned, not all fires are registered in the national database, but the majority of larger incidents are most likely included. The spring months (March to May) represent a high-hazard period for WUI fires in Norway, with 76% of cases occurring in just these 3 months. The statistics presented in this paper show that human activity is a key contributor to vegetation fires that spread to buildings. This highlights the need for targeted public education regarding fire prevention, particularly concerning human factors such as outdoor grilling and prescribed burns.

A recent study from Sweden [23] has found that living in a sparsely populated area increases vulnerability to wildfire. With the Scandinavian countries being similar in many ways, it could be reasonable to expect the same correlation in Norway, and our data set on a county level suggests that this was also the case here (Figure 1). Interestingly, when studying the data more detailed on a municipal level (Figure 2), such a correlation was not found. A correlation was, however, found between the number

of WUI fires per inhabitant and the number of buildings per area. We explain this by the buffer zones that often are created between vegetation and manmade structures when there are many buildings in an area, which in turn can reduce the WUI hazard.

The data of vegetation fires damaging two or more structures indicate that direct flame contact is the primary mode of spread, rather than flying embers. This aligns with a recent study from Sweden [19], indicating that the predominant spread mechanism in Scandinavia (direct flame contact) diverges from that observed elsewhere, where embers are found to be a critical component when wildfires spread to buildings, as shown, for example, in Fort McMurray, Canada, by Westhaver [17] and Witch and Guejito, USA, by Maranghides et al. [18].

4.2 | Recommendations for Statistics

The statistical analysis conducted in this study highlights a critical gap in the national fire statistics of Norway, where data on what caused the first vegetation ignition and which fire spread mechanisms caused the building to catch fire are not systematically collected. To effectively characterize wildfire hazards and reduce vulnerabilities, we recommend that authorities mandate the registration of these two key factors for all WUI incidents affecting structures.

Additionally, it is important to record data on the fire's location, local vegetation, fuel moisture content, and fire intensity. Environmental conditions such as wind speed, temperature, humidity, and recent precipitation should also be documented.

This enhancement in data collection will facilitate improved wildfire preparedness and response strategies in wildland-urban interface areas.

4.3 | Characterizing Wildfire Hazards Based on Field Studies

This study provided examples of fire dynamics of fires in low vegetation in Norway, which differ significantly from international patterns where the fires often have a higher intensity, such as crown fires [24]. The field exercises in Kvam and Drangedal showed that the fire spread rate of grass fires ranged from 0.22 to 0.39 m/min at FMC levels of 26%–38% and increased under drier conditions, reaching 0.6–1.3 m/min at FMC levels of 11%–25%. These measured flame spreads were considerably slow compared with the 121 grass fire experiments performed in Australia in 2017, with a lower FMC of 5%–11% and a higher wind speed average of 4.2 m/s [25]. Under these conditions, the flame spread rate averaged 59 m/min, greatly exceeding the spread rates recorded in Norway. Studies of grassfires in Sweden have shown a rate of spread from below 1 m/min to over 15 m/min, where the highest spread rates were measured in April and the lower values in May [26]. The wind speed and the moisture content of the upper layer of grass litter were similar over the 2 months, and the reduced fire spread rates measured in May compared with April were put in the context of the growing degree-days, that is, the fires spread more slowly when there was more green and fresh vegetation.

The flame front spread rate observed for the bog bilberry in the Drangedal fieldwork was 0.5 m/min, which is in the lower region of typical observations of shrubland wildfire spread in the literature. Studies of heather-dominated landscapes have shown rates of spread in the region 0.4–12.6 m/min [27–29], and studies of different types of shrublands in Portugal and Nova Scotia, Canada, have displayed rates of spread of 0.7–20 m/min [30] and 2–14 m/min [31], respectively. The recorded heat flux levels (1.3–12.5 kW/m²) in Kvam were also relatively low compared with reported values from medium-scale surface fire experiments [32], where peak convective heat fluxes range from 4 to 300 kW/m² and radiant heat fluxes from 1.5 to 300 kW/m².

Despite the high moisture content of the vegetation in the Kvam and Drangedal field exercises, the fires did spread naturally in the landscape, and post-flaming smoldering fires were observed in both exercises. Although the fires were relatively small in a wildfire context, they have the potential to expand and cause great damage, especially if weather conditions become warmer, drier, and windier while there is still residual smoldering. This demonstrates the importance of post-fire hot spot monitoring for several days after flame-out. The observed fire patterns of relatively low flame heights, low-intensity fires, and residual smoldering indicate that Norwegian wildfires may be difficult to detect by a detection system set up for high-intensity wildfires. Adjustments to the detection protocols to account for local conditions are recommended.

The overgrowth of juniper in Norwegian coastal landscapes adds complexity to managing these fires, as field observations have shown. Additionally, shifts in farming practices combined

with limited knowledge on prescribed burning have resulted in unmaintained cultural landscapes and an accumulation of fuel. This highlights the need for increased knowledge and training in prescribed fire management. These findings align with previous research on wildfires in Norway's coastal heathlands [33], which also emphasized the importance of prescribed burns for mitigating and handling WUI fire risks.

Importantly, the prescribed burn exercises in this study not only served as training opportunities but also provided controlled conditions for empirical fire behavior analysis, including fire spread rates and post-fire smoldering observations. By allowing for free-burning sections within the controlled burns, these exercises simulated real wildfire conditions in a safe and measurable environment. The data collected contribute directly to understanding wildfire hazards in WUI areas and informing fire management strategies.

Additionally, this study examined a winter wildfire in Roan, which shared many characteristics with other winter wildfires in Frøya, Flatanger, and Lærdal [7, 34–36]. In all these cases, dry conditions combined with strong winds resulted in unexpectedly intense fires, demonstrating that winter wildfires can be just as hazardous as those occurring in warmer seasons.

4.4 | Reducing Vulnerabilities and Safeguarding WUI Zones

Key strategies to safeguard WUI areas on a community level include recognizing the unique challenges posed by scattered rural populations and the significant distances that fire services may need to cover, as illustrated by the Roan case study. Empowering residents to take proactive measures in making their properties more fire safe is crucial, especially in instances where fire services may be delayed or otherwise occupied. Recommendations for Norway can draw inspiration from the aforementioned international guidelines (e.g., FireWise [14] and FireSmart [15]), but also consider the learning points presented in this study. Simple and cost-effective measures to reduce fire risk can include clearing debris from roofs, gutters, and decks, storing flammable items away from the house, sealing roof eaves and vents with ember-proof mesh, and regularly maintaining lawns by clearing dead vegetation. These actions will help minimize the hazard of fire spread to houses.

To effectively safeguard WUI areas, various solutions must be documented and compared through relevant experimental methods that assess relevant fire behavior. As shown through our fieldwork, it is particularly important to not underestimate the potential hazards of wildfires in low vegetation and to avoid the hazard of high-intensity ladder species such as juniper. As shown by the historical data, focus on direct flame contact is key. Once national and local WUI guidelines are established, substantial efforts will be necessary to engage local communities and ensure the implementation of preventive measures. A recent study from a wildfire-prone region in southern Sweden [37] illustrates this issue; although residents recognize the heightened risk of wildfires, they do not view it as a threat to the community's future well-being. Additionally, forest owners and homeowners show a low level of commitment to implementing

preventive or adaptive measures. Similar challenges would also be expected in Norway.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings from historical data of this study are available from BRIS by DSB and Statistics Norway. The majority of the field exercise data that support the findings will be available in the project's online repository. Other data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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